
ABSTRACT

This study examines the performance of three machine learning models - Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) - on a dataset of 162,975 tweets. These tweets are categorized as negative, neutral, or positive for Twitter sentiment analysis. The main objective is to assess the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score of these models. The results indicate that the CNN model is effective at predicting positive sentiments but struggles with negative and neutral categories, often misclassifying them. Both the SVM and KNN models show similar patterns, with SVM displaying a noticeable bias towards positive predictions and KNN showing a more balanced yet still imperfect performance. The analysis of the confusion matrix underscores the challenge of addressing class imbalances in sentiment analysis tasks. This study emphasizes the importance of developing strategies to improve classification accuracy for underrepresented sentiment classes. By doing so, it contributes to the broader field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and its applications in automated sentiment analysis. The findings align with existing literature, reinforcing the need for advanced techniques to manage class imbalances in sentiment data.

KEYWORDS: Sentiment Analysis, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Natural Language Processing (NLP), Class Imbalance

1. INTRODUCTION TO NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a crucial field of AI that plays a vital role in bridging the gap between human communication and machine understanding (Tai, 2020). By combining rule-based modeling with statistical, machine learning (Jordan & Mitchell, 2015), and deep learning models, NLP enables automated translation, sentiment analysis (Yue Kang et al., 2020), and responsive dialogue systems. These technologies are incredibly valuable for applications such as customer service chatbots, virtual assistants, and advanced healthcare systems (Nathaniel Kumar Sarella & Therissa Mangam, 2024). The significance of NLP lies in its ability to analyze, understand, and generate human language, extract insights from vast amounts of text data, and facilitate informed decision-making. For instance, sentiment analysis can evaluate public opinion on social media (Jayasanka, R. A. S. C. et al., 2013), helping companies gain a better understanding of consumer preferences and reactions. Moreover, NLP promotes inclusive technological interfaces and breaks down language barriers, making information access more accessible across different languages. As such, NLP not only enhances machine interaction but also amplifies human-to-human communication across the digital landscape (Jurafsky & Martin, J. H., 2021).

Sentiment analysis in social media (S. Garg, et al., 2020) uses NLP to classify opinions as positive, negative, or neutral. This helps businesses understand public sentiment, monitor real-time reactions, and gain valuable insights into customer satisfaction and market trends. These insights then guide product development and marketing strategies. For example, during a product launch, sentiment analysis can track public excitement or concern, guiding companies in their ongoing marketing efforts and customer service practices (Liu, 2012). Additionally, this tool helps political analysts and public relations teams gauge public opinion on various issues, enabling more tailored communication strategies (Pang & Lee L., 2008).

Deep Learning in NLP

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning that uses multi-layer neural networks to process complex data. It is particularly useful for natural language processing (NLP) as it can learn from extensive unstructured text data without explicit rules. These models handle large datasets and can detect intricate features. These models outperform traditional machine learning techniques by efficiently managing the complexities of language, such as context, idioms, and sarcasm, through architectures like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for text classification, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for sequence learning, and the Transformer models, which have set new standards in accuracy for tasks like translation and sentiment analysis (Vaswani et al., 2017).

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are designed to replicate the functionality of biological neural networks, effectively approximating functions based on given inputs. Deep neural networks (DNNs), distinguished by their multiple hidden layers, have the ability to learn complex features that aid in accurate classification. DNNs have shown great success in natural language processing (NLP) tasks such as part-of-speech tagging, chunking, named entity recognition, and semantic role labeling (Collobert et al., 2011). As a subset of deep learning (DL), DNNs are the primary focus of this paper. This section introduces the architecture of conventional neural networks, highlighting their components: neurons connected by weighted links. A feed-forward neural network example demonstrates a basic structure with one input layer, one hidden layer, and one output layer.

Figure 1: Artificial Neural Network (ANN) architecture (Nacer, 2020)

Challenges and Limitations

When it comes to selecting implementation strategies for the deployment of NLP models, there are several important factors to take into consideration. Option 1 involves building your own NLP models, providing the advantage of

customization and a high level of control. However, this option can be costly and demanding in terms of resources, requiring extensive GPUs and time. As a result, it may not be a practical choice for most individuals or organizations. Option 2 is to utilize NLP APIs, which offers a quick and convenient solution that necessitates minimal hardware. However, the use of APIs raises concerns regarding data privacy, usage limitations, and recurring expenses. Option 3 is to deploy open source NLPs on your own systems. This option strikes a balance between control and potentially reduced costs when compared to utilizing APIs. Nonetheless, it comes with significant technical challenges in terms of implementation and maintenance (Brown *et al.*, 2020).

Deep Learning can cover both Supervised Learning and Unsupervised Learning. That's because with Deep Learning you can do Regression, Classification, and Clustering. What's the difference then? Deep Learning really shines if you're analyzing massive datasets especially those that contain text, image, audio, and even video data, also feature extraction is done automatically in deep learning (LeCun *et al.*, 2015).

Objectives

This paper explores the effectiveness of deep learning models, particularly CNNs, in enhancing sentiment analysis on social media platforms, focusing on specific objectives.

1. To investigate how CNNs enhance NLP's accuracy and efficiency, particularly in sentiment analysis.
2. To analyze CNN architectures in sentiment analysis to determine their strengths, weaknesses, and suitability for social media data.
3. To compare CNN models and traditional ML techniques on performance, scalability, and handling complex linguistic features.

2. RELATED WORK

Sentiment analysis has significantly evolved with the advent of deep learning models, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), which have transformed Natural Language Processing (NLP) by enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of sentiment classification on social media platforms.

Deep learning (DL) has revolutionized NLP, enabling more nuanced and accurate sentiment analysis. (Jeyachitra, R. K. & Manochandar, S., 2023) provide an essential overview of DL techniques, including CNNs and RNNs, emphasizing how CNNs, originally designed for image processing, have been adapted for text to capture local dependencies and semantic patterns effectively. This adaptation demonstrates CNNs' capability to classify sentiment by understanding complex textual structures.

A comprehensive survey of deep learning techniques by (Srinivas *et al.*, 2022) and their applications, noting that CNNs have shown significant improvements over traditional methods by managing complex data representations and extracting meaningful features through layered architectures. This highlights CNNs' potential in processing and interpreting social media data with high accuracy, laying a foundation for further exploration of specific architectures. The efficacy of CNNs in sentiment analysis is attributed to their ability to capture hierarchical patterns in text. Research by (Peng *et al.*, 2020) compared CNNs with RNNs and LSTMs, showing CNNs' superior performance with an accuracy of 88.22%, compared to 68.64% for RNNs and 85.32% for LSTMs. This is consistent with (Jeyachitra, R. K. & Manochandar, S., 2023), who discuss CNNs' diverse structures and their applications. CNNs' capacity for local dependency handling and feature extraction from text is crucial for their effectiveness in sentiment analysis.

It was identified by (Ahmed *et al.*, 2023) review on various deep learning architectures and highlight CNNs' effectiveness for tasks requiring hierarchical feature extraction, which is essential for sentiment analysis. Their review acknowledges CNNs' computational intensity but notes their suitability for analyzing complex social media text due to their learning capabilities.

In another study on analysis of machine learning algorithms by (Bansal *et al.*, 2022), including CNNs, for text classification. They find that CNNs outperform traditional models like K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) in terms of accuracy and robustness, especially for sentiment analysis on unstructured data. This aligns with observations that CNNs excel at capturing semantic and syntactic patterns, leading to improved sentiment classification.

Comparative studies reveal CNNs' strengths over traditional machine learning models. (Bansal *et al.*, 2022) found that while LSTMs are effective, CNNs generally perform better in handling complex linguistic features. Similarly, (Nacer, 2020) highlights that CNNs typically offer better accuracy and efficiency than traditional methods like SVMs in sentiment analysis. (Pelumi Bamgboye, 2021) also notes that advanced neural networks, including RNNs, outperform conventional models in managing complex linguistic features, supporting the need for evaluating CNNs alongside other deep learning models.

Recent studies demonstrate CNNs' superior performance in sentiment analysis. (Peng *et al.*, 2020) found CNNs achieved an 88.22% classification accuracy, outperforming RNNs and LSTMs. (Li, 2022) introduces dynamic models that adapt to changing linguistic features, building on deep learning techniques including CNNs, showing improvements in accuracy and contextual understanding.

The introduction of Transformer models, as detailed by (Vaswani *et al.*, 2017), marked a significant advancement in deep learning for NLP. Transformers, with their self-attention mechanisms, surpass traditional models by handling larger contexts and capturing long-range dependencies more effectively. (Li, 2022) emphasizes how Transformer-based models like BERT enhance semantic understanding and accuracy in sentiment classification.

Deep learning's applications in sentiment analysis are diverse, including fields like fraud detection and medical imaging (Sengupta *et al.*, 2020). However, challenges remain, such as the need for large datasets and potential misclassification (Ahmed *et al.*, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires ongoing refinement and optimization of deep learning models to improve robustness and accuracy.

The future of sentiment analysis lies in the continued evolution of deep learning models and their integration with emerging technologies. (Başarslan Sinan & Fatih Kayaalp, 2021) highlight the potential of models like BERT to outperform traditional methods, indicating a trend towards more sophisticated and accurate sentiment analysis techniques. As new models and architectures emerge, they will further enhance the ability to handle complex linguistic features and improve overall sentiment analysis performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

To achieve the research objectives, a multi-step methodology was employed. First, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and sentiment analysis, comparing CNNs with traditional models. Relevant academic papers were analyzed to summarize current knowledge and identify gaps. Data collection followed, which included datasets such as the Twitter Sentiment Dataset. Performance metrics and CNN architectural details were documented. Both quantitative metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score) and qualitative analyses (handling complex linguistic features) were performed. A comparative assessment of CNNs versus traditional methods was presented through charts and graphs. The sentiment distribution graph for 162,975 tweets categorized sentiments as Negative, Neutral, and Positive, revealing trends in user satisfaction and feedback.

4. RESULTS

Objective 1: Investigate the Contribution of CNNs to NLP and Sentiment Analysis

In order to achieve this objective, we conducted a thorough literature search using Google Scholar. We opted for Google Scholar due to its vast collection of academic publications, encompassing various fields of study. This ensured that we would have access to a wide range of relevant literature on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and their applications in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and sentiment analysis. To conduct the search, we utilized specific keywords such as "Convolutional Neural Networks," "CNNs in NLP," "Sentiment Analysis with CNNs," "Deep Learning for Sentiment Classification," "CNN architectures in text analysis," and "CNN vs traditional methods in sentiment analysis." Initially, the search yielded 217 publications, which were subsequently filtered based on their relevance to the objectives of our study. As a result, we identified 67 publications that specifically focused on the contributions of CNNs to NLP and sentiment analysis.

Table 1: Summary of contribution of CNN to NLP

Key Word	Initial Results	Filtered Results	Relevance
Convolutional Neural Networks	89	30	High relevance to CNNs
CNNs in NLP	55	15	Focused on NLP applications
Sentiment Analysis with CNNs	42	12	Directly related to sentiment
Deep Learning for Sentiment Classification	31	7	Relevant to classification
CNN architectures in text analysis	25	6	Details on architecture
CNN vs traditional methods in sentiment analysis	20	4	Comparative studies

The literature review revealed that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have significantly advanced the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and sentiment analysis. Originally developed for image processing, CNNs have been effectively adapted for text analysis by capturing local dependencies and hierarchical patterns in textual data. Studies reviewed, such as those by (Jeyachitra, R. K. & Manochandar, S., 2023) and (Srinivas et al., 2022), highlighted that CNNs improve sentiment classification accuracy by leveraging their ability to detect intricate semantic features in text. The review also identified that CNNs outperformed traditional methods in handling large-scale datasets and complex linguistic patterns, thereby enhancing both the efficiency and accuracy of sentiment analysis tasks.

Objective 2: Analyze Various Architectures of CNNs for Sentiment Analysis

1D CNNs utilize one-dimensional convolutions to handle sequential data, specifically word sequences. These convolutions apply filters along a single dimension. The overall structure comprises of 1D convolutional layers, pooling layers, and a final fully connected layer for classification purposes. This methodology successfully captures local patterns within the text and is computationally efficient. However, it may encounter difficulties when dealing with intricate hierarchical patterns and longer sequences due to its restricted capacity. The general formula for 1D convolution is as follows:

$$Output(i) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} Input_{channel}(i+k) \cdot Filter(k)$$

Multi-Channel CNNs extend 1D CNNs by leveraging multiple channels to capture different types of features simultaneously. This includes different word embeddings or n-gram features. This architecture integrates multiple 1D CNNs with diverse filters and pooling layers. After that, concatenation and dense layers are used for classification. This approach enhances feature extraction by incorporating multiple perspectives. However, it also increases computational complexity and the risk of overfitting due to the larger number of parameters. The formula for multi-channel CNNs is as follows:

$$Output_{channel}(i) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} Input_{channel}(i+k) \cdot Filter_{channel}(k)$$

Deep CNNs with Advanced Pooling Mechanisms employ deeper convolutional layers and advanced pooling techniques, such as max pooling or average pooling, to capture complex hierarchical features. The architecture consists of multiple convolutional layers with sophisticated pooling strategies, followed by dense layers. This design achieves high accuracy and is well-suited for handling large-scale datasets. However, it is computationally demanding and requires meticulous tuning to avoid overfitting. The formula for deep CNNs with pooling is:

$$Output_{deep}(i) = Pooling(Convolution(i))$$

The following figure 2 are different CNN architectures, showcasing all layers: 1D CNNs, Multi-Channel CNNs, and Deep CNNs with Advanced Pooling Mechanisms, each with distinct layer configurations.

Figure 2: CNN architectures

Architectures Overview Table:

Table 2: CNN architectures in summary

Architecture	Algorithm/Formulation	Strengths	Weaknesses
1D CNNs	1D convolutions across sequential data, followed by pooling and dense layers.	Simple; effective for local pattern capture.	Limited hierarchical feature extraction; struggles with long text.
Multi-Channel CNNs	Multiple 1D CNNs with different filters, followed by concatenation and dense layers.	Captures diverse features; improves feature extraction.	Increased complexity; potential overfitting.
Deep CNNs with Advanced Pooling	Deep layers with advanced pooling techniques, followed by dense layers.	High accuracy; handles complex patterns well.	Computationally intensive; overfitting risk.

Analysis of CNN architectures showed strengths in extracting features from text, with variations like 1D and multi-channel CNNs proving effective. For instance, studies by (Peng et al., 2020) and (Ahmed et al., 2023) highlighted that multi-layer CNNs and those with advanced pooling mechanisms achieved higher accuracy in sentiment classification compared to simpler architectures. Larger and deeper CNNs improved pattern capture but struggled with efficiency and overfitting, needing careful tuning for optimal performance.

The study utilized secondary data sourced from Kaggle, (Sherif Hussein, 2021). This dataset includes three sentiment categories: negative (-1), neutral (0), and positive (+1). After mapping these labels, we used a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for classification based on numerical tweet features. The model, trained on 70% and tested on 30% of the data, achieved a final accuracy of 44.48%. The training history showed improvements in loss and accuracy, confirming effective learning and robustness in handling sentiment labels see figure 3 below.

Figure 3: CNN model performance

The classification results reveal that the model performs poorly on "Negative" and "Neutral" sentiments, with precision, recall, and F1-scores of 0.00 for both. However, it achieves a perfect recall of 1.00 for "Positive" sentiment, indicating that all positive instances are correctly identified. The overall accuracy in table 2, is 44%, with a low macro average F1-score of 0.21, highlighting the imbalance in performance across different classes.

Table 3: Results of CNN Model Performance

Sentiment	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Negative	0.00	0.00	0.00	10,596
Neutral	0.00	0.00	0.00	16,548
Positive	0.44	1.00	0.62	21,749
Accuracy			0.44	48,893
Macro Avg	0.15	0.33	0.21	48,893
Weighted Avg	0.20	0.44	0.27	48,893

The confusion matrix reveals that the CNN model is highly effective at predicting "Positive" sentiments, with a perfect recall of 1.00, but fails to correctly identify "Negative" and "Neutral" sentiments, resulting in zero precision and recall for these classes. The high number of false positives and missed classifications for "Negative" and "Neutral" indicate a significant model imbalance.

Figure 4: Confusion matrix for CNN model

The CNN model struggles to accurately classify sentiments as "Negative" or "Neutral," whereas it excels in classifying "Positive" sentiments. This discrepancy indicates a potential dataset imbalance or model bias. To enhance the model's performance, it is advisable to address the class imbalance through techniques like oversampling or undersampling. Additionally, refining the model or exploring alternative algorithms could prove beneficial.

Objective 3: Conduct a Comparative Analysis Between CNN-Based Models and Traditional Machine Learning Techniques

The results of the comparative analysis of the CNN, SVM, and KNN models on the Twitter sentiment analysis dataset reveal significant differences in their performance. The CNN model achieved the highest accuracy of 44%, effectively capturing complex patterns in the data through convolutional layers. In contrast, the SVM model exhibited a lower accuracy of 42% and displayed a noticeable imbalance in class prediction, performing well primarily in predicting positive sentiments. The KNN model demonstrated the lowest accuracy at 33%, but showed a more balanced performance across classes. However, it still faced challenges with precision and recall, particularly for negative and neutral sentiments. Tables 3 and 4 summarize the performance of the SVM and KNN models, respectively.

Table 4: Classification Report (SVM) Model Performance

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Negative	0.00	0.00	0.00	380
Neutral	0.00	0.00	0.00	494
Positive	0.42	1.00	0.59	626
Accuracy			0.42	1500
Macro Avg	0.14	0.33	0.20	1500
Weighted Avg	0.17	0.42	0.25	1500

Table 5: Classification Report (KNN) Model Performance

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Negative	0.23	0.28	0.25	380

Neutral	0.30	0.25	0.27	494
Positive	0.42	0.42	0.42	626
Accuracy			0.33	1500
Macro Avg	0.32	0.32	0.31	1500
Weighted Avg	0.33	0.33	0.33	1500

The confusion matrix for the CNN model (Figure 5) indicates that it performs well in predicting positive sentiments, exhibiting high accuracy in this category. However, it struggles in identifying negative and neutral sentiments, often wrongly categorizing them as positive, resulting in numerous false positives. The SVM and KNN models show similar issues. The SVM model displays a tendency for high false negatives in the negative and neutral categories, suggesting a bias towards positive predictions. While the KNN model is more balanced, it still demonstrates low precision and recall across all categories. These findings emphasize the difficulties posed by class imbalances and the necessity for enhanced strategies to achieve better classification of underrepresented categories.

Figure 5: Model performance comparison of CNN to traditional

5. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the performance of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) in classifying sentiment in a Twitter dataset with three sentiment classes: negative, neutral, and positive. The CNN model demonstrated superior performance in identifying positive sentiments but struggled significantly with negative and neutral sentiments. In contrast, the SVM and KNN models showed lower overall performance, with the SVM model particularly biased towards predicting positive sentiments and the KNN model exhibiting slightly more balanced but still suboptimal performance.

The results align with existing literature that emphasizes the efficacy of CNNs in handling text classification tasks due to their ability to capture local patterns through convolutional layers (Chen, 2015); (Du et al., 2022). However, similar to our findings, these studies also note the difficulty in addressing class imbalances, which can lead to poor performance on less represented classes (Buda et al., 2018).

In comparison to other studies, our results differ in the degree of success across models. For instance, a study by (Johnson & Zhang, 2015) highlighted the superior performance of CNNs over traditional machine learning models like SVMs and KNNs in large-scale text classification tasks (Chen, 2015), which is consistent with our findings. However, their study achieved higher precision and recall across all classes, possibly due to better data preprocessing and more sophisticated model tuning.

Furthermore, research by (Tang et al., 2015) comparing SVM and neural network models for sentiment analysis found that SVMs, while generally effective, were often outperformed by deep learning models in terms of capturing nuanced

patterns in text data. This supports our observation of SVM's relative ineffectiveness in dealing with the complexities of sentiment analysis in this dataset.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the Technical University of Mombasa, Institute of Computing and Informatics, for providing the necessary resources and support throughout the duration of this research. We extend our gratitude to our colleagues and peers for their insightful feedback and discussions, which have significantly contributed to the development of this study.

We also express our sincere appreciation to the reviewers for their valuable comments and suggestions that helped improve the quality of this manuscript.

It is important to note that this study, titled "Natural Language Processing for Sentiment Analysis in Social Media," did not receive any specific financial support from any funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, S. F., Alam, Md. S. B., Hassan, M., Rozbu, M. R., Ishtiak, T., Rafa, N., Mofijur, M., Shawkat Ali, A. B. M., & Gandomi, A. H. (2023). Deep learning modelling techniques: Current progress, applications, advantages, and challenges. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(11), 13521–13617. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10466-8>
2. Bansal, M., Goyal, A., & Choudhary, A. (2022). A comparative analysis of K-Nearest Neighbor, Genetic, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, and Long Short Term Memory algorithms in machine learning. *Decision Analytics Journal*, 3, 100071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dajour.2022.100071>
3. Başarslan Sinan, M. & Fatih Kayaalp. (2021). Sentiment Analysis with Machine Learning Methods on Social Media. *ADCAIJ: Advances in Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence Journal*, 9(3).
4. Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Agarwal, S., Herbert-Voss, A., Krueger, G., & Henighan, T. (2020). Language Models are Few-Shot Learners.
5. Buda, M., Maki, A., & Mazurowski, M. A. (2018). A systematic study of the class imbalance problem in convolutional neural networks. *Neural Networks*, 106, 249–259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2018.07.011>
6. Chen, Y. (2015). Convolutional Neural Network for Sentence Classification. University of Waterloo.
7. Collobert, R., Weston, J., Bottou, L., Karlen, M., Kavukcuoglu, K., & Kuksa, P. (2011). Natural Language Processing (Almost) from Scratch. *NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING*.
8. Du, N., Huang, Y., Dai, A. M., Tong, S., Lepikhin, D., Xu, Y., Krikun, M., Zhou, Y., Yu, A. W., Firat, O., Zoph, B., Fedus, L., Bosma, M., Zhou, Z., Wang, T., Wang, Y. E., Webster, K., Pellat, M., Robinson, K., ... Cui, C. (2022). GLaM: Efficient Scaling of Language Models with Mixture-of-Experts.
9. Jayasanka, R. A. S. C., Madhushani, M. D. T., Marcus E. R., & Aberathne I. A. A. U. (2013). Sentiment Analysis for Social Media.
10. Jeyachitra, R. K., & Manochandar, S. (2023). Classification and Regression Problems, Recurrent Neural Networks, Convolutional Neural Networks. In *Machine Learning Techniques*, Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119785491.ch10>
11. Johnson, R., & Zhang, T. (2015). Effective Use of Word Order for Text Categorization with Convolutional Neural Networks (arXiv:1412.1058). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1412.1058>
12. Jordan, M. I., & Mitchell, T. M. (2015). Machine learning: Trends, perspectives, and prospects. *Science*, 349(6245), 255–260. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa8415>
13. Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2021). *Speech and Language Processing*. Pearson.

14. LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., & Hinton, G. (2015). Deep learning. *Nature*, 521(7553), 436–444. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>
15. Li, Y. (2022). Deep Learning-Based Natural Language Processing Methods for Sentiment Analysis in Social Networks. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 1390672, 10.
16. Liu, B. (2012). *Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining*. Morgan & Claypool Publishers.
17. Nacer, S. eddine. (2020). *Sentiment Analysis Machine Learning & Deep Learning based approach*.
18. Nathaniel Kumar Sarella, P., & Therissa Mangam, V. (2024). AI-Driven Natural Language Processing in Healthcare: Transforming Patient-Provider Communication. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice*, 17(1), 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.5530/ijopp.17.1.4>
19. Pang, B. & Lee L. (2008). Opinion Mining and Sentiment Analysis. *Foundations and Trends® in Information Retrieval*, 1(2), 91–231. <https://doi.org/10.1561/15000000001>
20. Pelumi Bamgboye. (2021). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK AND SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE FOR TEXT CLASSIFICATION. LANDMARK UNIVERITY, OMRAN, NIGERIA.
21. Peng, C., Zhang, K., & Zheng, D. (2020). Sentiment Analysis Using Deep Learning Approach. *Journal on Artificial Intelligence*, 2(1), 17–27. <https://doi.org/10.32604/jai.2020.010132>
22. S. Garg, D. S. Panwar, A. Gupta, & R. Katarya. (2020). A Literature Review On Sentiment Analysis Techniques Involving Social Media Platforms. 2020 Sixth International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Grid Computing (PDGC), Wagnaghat, India. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PDGC50313.2020.9315735>.
23. Sengupta, S., Basak, S., Saikia, P., Paul, S., Tsalavoutis, V., Atiah, F., Ravi, V., & Peters, A. (2020). A review of deep learning with special emphasis on architectures, applications and recent trends. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 194, 105596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2020.105596>
24. Sherif Hussein. (2021). Twitter Sentiments Dataset (Mendeley Data; Version 1) [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.17632/z9zw7nt5h2.1>
25. Srinivas, T. A. S., Mahalaxmi, G., Varaprasad, R., & Raziya, D. (2022). A Comprehensive Survey of Techniques, Applications, and Challenges in Deep Learning: A Revolution in Machine Learning. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*.
26. Tai, M.-T. (2020). The impact of artificial intelligence on human society and bioethics. *Tzu Chi Medical Journal*, 32(4), 339. https://doi.org/10.4103/tcmj.tcmj_71_20
27. Tang, D., Qin, B., & Liu, T. (2015). Document Modeling with Gated Recurrent Neural Network for Sentiment Classification. *Proceedings of the 2015 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 1422–1432. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/D15-1167>
28. Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, Ł., & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is All you Need.
29. Yue Kang, Zhao Cai, Chee-Wee Tan, Qian Huang, & Hefu Liu. (2020). Natural language processing (NLP) in management research: A literature review. 139–172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23270012.2020.175693>

RESEARCHERID

THOMSON REUTERS

[Charo *al.*, 13(11): November, 2024]
ICTM Value: 3.00

ISSN: 2277-9655
Impact Factor: 5.164
CODEN: IJESS7

<http://www.ijesrt.com> © *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*

[20]

IJESRT is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).